

1 Processing Strategies to Obtain Highly Porous Silk Fibroin structures 2 with Tailored Microstructure and Molecular Characteristics and Their 3 Applicability in Water Remediation

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18 **Abstract:** The present work reports on the control of silk fibroin (SF) porous structures
19 performance through various processing methods. The study includes the analysis of two
20 dissolving techniques (CaCl₂/H₂O/EtOH ternary and LiBr/H₂O binary solutions), three
21 regeneration methods (gelation, lyophilization and gas foaming) and one post-processing
22 (EtOH treatment). In all the cases, followed steps enable obtaining SF structures with
23 porosity values above 94% and large surface areas.

24 Results about samples microstructure, secondary organization, crystallinity and water
25 behavior reveal a direct correlation between processing and SF properties.

26 Thanks to the achieved progress, porous structures were evaluated for metalloids (As⁵⁺
27 and As³⁺) and heavy metals (Cr⁶⁺ and Cr³⁺) adsorption, observing a relationship between
28 ionic species adsorption ability and the processing derived behavior.

29 Thus, it is shown that the control of the properties of SF based porous structures through
30 processing, represents a suitable and ecofriendly approach for the development of bio-
31 based materials for environmental applications.

32
33 **Keywords:** Silk fibroin; porous microstructure; adsorption mechanism, heavy metals
34 removal; water remediation.

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Sustainability is a global priority implying the proper use of global resources and the
37 reduction of non-renewable materials dependence [1, 2]. In particular, oil-based materials
38 lead to a large environmental impact related to extraction procedures, combustion and
39 waste management [3]. Thus, it becomes essential to redirect efforts towards the
40 development of a new generation of materials able to respond to the technological
41 demands, by matching the advantages of synthetic materials, but supporting the
42 decreasing of current pollution levels [4].

43 In this scope, bio-based materials obtained from natural resources appear as an interesting
44 alternative. Among them, Silk Fibroin (SF) a polypeptide fiber found in the cocoons of
45 *Bombyx mori* silkworms, and used in fabrics for more than 3000 years [5, 6], represents
46 an interesting option, due to its natural origin, availability and physical-chemical
47 properties [7]. SF shows excellent thermal and chemical stability, high mechanical
48 strength, biodegradability and facile processing [14]. Also, it is possible to enlarge SF
49 applicability by varying its structure in the form of fibers [8], films [9], particles [8], non-
50 woven mats [10] and tri-dimensional (3D) porous structures, among others [11]. Thanks
51 to that, it has been possible to apply SF in electronics [12, 13], sensors and actuators [9,
52 14], biomedicine [15] and environmental remediation [16-18].

53 Among others applications, SF has become a promising material in the environmental
54 field, where has been used as filtration and decontamination media [16, 19]. However,
55 there is still a lack of knowledge around how processing procedure affects SF based
56 materials microstructure and properties, which is particularly relevant for the
57 improvement of SF for specific applications [20].

58 As a protein, SF consists on repetitive amino acid sequences mainly composed by two
59 polypeptide chains with different molecular weight, a 390-kDa heavy chain (H-Chain)
60 and 26-kDa light chain (L-Chain) [5, 6], bonded together by a single disulfide bond [15].
61 H-chains are related with repetitive G(Glycine)-A(alanine)-G-A-G-X hydrophobic motifs
62 (crystalline domains), while L-chains are related to non-repetitive hydrophilic ones
63 (amorphous region) [16]. This amphiphilic organization based on hydrophilic–
64 hydrophobic–hydrophilic blocks confers SF a similar behavior to that observed for
65 triblock-copolymers in solution [21].

66 During secondary folding, SF polypeptide chains adopt different conformations, which
67 strongly influence the final behavior of SF. These configurations are i) random coil (RC),
68 composed by non-ordered domains; ii) α -helix (A), a ordered region based on a tight

69 single polypeptide chain with helix conformation; iii) β -sheets (B), which are two
70 dimensional sheet-like ordered regions of folded polypeptide chains linked by hydrogen-
71 bonds (Figure 1b); iv) β -turns (T), a non-ordered domains implied on β -sheets linking
72 and v) side chains (SC), which are peptide residues non-implied in bonding.

73 There are three known different crystalline conformations of SF named Silk I, Silk II and
74 Silk III [22]. Silk I can be defined as the precursor structure of β -crystals, is formed by a
75 mainly ordered structure (composed by G-A-G-A-G- repetitive motif) in where the
76 complete packing is hindered by interactions between water molecules and ordered
77 domains. As a consequence, Silk I shows a metastable conformation easy to be
78 solubilized. Silk II is a highly packed structure and results from Silk I stabilization by
79 bonded-water molecules loss. Ordered domains packing into silk II leads to the formation
80 of non-soluble β -sheets, which give to the structure stability [23]. Silk III is an uncommon
81 threefold helical crystal structure formed at the air-water interface [24].

82 During SF regeneration, β -crystals from several polypeptide chains packing are formed.
83 As a result, SF structure adopts a cross-linked conformation where β -crystals act as nodes
84 linking the amorphous regions. The high stability of β -crystal nodes, enables the overall
85 structure integrity, while wrinkled amorphous domains provide mobility, elasticity and
86 flexibility [25, 26]. Both crystalline and amorphous domains presence and relation into
87 cross-slinked structure, as well as crystalline domains organization and non-folded chains
88 amphiphilic behavior, mainly define the SF materials characteristics. Accordingly, they
89 represents an interesting way to improve SF based materials applicability. Thus, in this
90 work their study and control has been prioritized.

91 Based on this idea, the present work has focused on establishing the effect of different
92 processing strategies to tailor SF microstructure and properties. For that, two dissolving
93 techniques ($\text{CaCl}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{EtOH}$ ternary and $\text{LiBr}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ binary solutions), three different
94 processing methods (gelification, lyophilization and gas foaming)[28-31] and one post-
95 processing (EtOH treatment), have been used to produce SF based porous structures and
96 tailor their properties. The followed different strategies respond to i) water-based solvents
97 low environmental impact [27], ii) processing methods allowed times previous samples
98 freeze-drying (gelation > lyophilization > gas foaming), which enables the study of
99 molecular recombination time effect on silk properties, iii) well proven use of EtOH as
100 β -sheets promoter [35] and iv) techniques low complexity and availability, which could
101 facilitate their implementation in future processes.

102 In order to prove the potential of the obtained results, water pollution by hazardous
103 contaminants has been tackled, as it represents a challenge due to the serious health
104 damages and the complexity of the most commonly used decontamination systems [32].
105 Among water pollutants, arsenic and chromium have been selected due to their varied
106 chemistry, high toxicity in aqueous environments, even at very low concentrations (they
107 are genotoxic, mutagenic, teratogenic and carcinogenic), non-biodegradability, high
108 mobility, long-term bio-persistence and anthropic presence on nature [2](**Chromium
109 speciation in Zr-based Metal-Organic Frameworks for environmental remediation**).
110 For water pollutants removal, the most novel and promising technology is based on
111 composite materials [33], based on an active phase on which the pollutant is adsorbed and
112 a non-active structure providing support and mechanical stability. Thus, comonly the
113 adsorption capacity of a composite system is mainly defined by the adsorption capacity
114 of active phase and the accessibility given by the holding phase, the latter depending on
115 its porosity [34]. Whereas most efforts in this area have been devoted to improving the
116 efficiency of the active phase, few efforts have been directed to improve the self-
117 adsorption properties of the porous structures. In this context and promoted by the
118 achieved control on SF porous structures properties and behavior, a proof of concept
119 centered on bio-based materials use for adsorption purposes has been addressed. The
120 obtained materials could be complemented with an active phase in order to mix both
121 components properties for polluted waters remediation. The idea is to show the Silk
122 Fibroin potentiality for adsorption applications, as well as the possibility to control bio-
123 based materials properties through simple and accessible techniques, in order to improve
124 their performance and promote their use.

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135 **2. Experimental details**

136 *2.1. Materials*

137 Silk Fibroin (SF) was extracted from *Bombyx mori* cocoons, supplied by APPACDM
138 from Castelo Branco (Portugal). Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), calcium chloride (CaCl_2)
139 and lithium bromide were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Dialysis tubes with a diameter
140 of 3 cm and molecular weight cut-of 3500 Daltons were obtained from Spectrum.

141

142 *2.2. Precursor solution preparation*

143 Porous structures were prepared from aqueous solutions of SF. The first step was the
144 extraction of SF from the *Bombyx mori* Silk cocoons. For this, the cocoons were dry-
145 cleaned and cut into small pieces of about 0.5 cm^2 . The pieces were then degummed twice
146 in 3.7 mM Na_2CO_3 aqueous solutions at 80-85 °C during 10 minutes in a silk-to-liquid
147 ratio of 1:40 (wt:v). Between first and second degumming the fibers were manually
148 opened to facilitate the process. The resulting SF was immersed three times in consecutive
149 distilled water baths and then rinsed thoroughly. The well-cleaned fibers were finally
150 dried in an oven at 40 °C for 24 h and then kept in dry until be used.

151 Afterwards, SF was dissolved by following two different procedure, as a result, two types
152 of aqueous SF solutions will be obtained. The main difference between both procedures
153 was the used solving agent: i) a $\text{CaCl}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{EtOH}$ ternary solution 1/8/2 molar in a silk-
154 to-liquid ratio of 1:10 wt:v and ii) 9.3 M $\text{LiBr}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ binary solution in a silk-to-liquid ratio
155 of 1:20 wt:v. In both cases, SF was dissolved for 2 h at 60 °C under magnetic stirring.
156 The obtained solutions were dialyzed against distilled water in a 3500 Da cutoff cellulose
157 cassette, with 3 water changes per day and until constant dialyzed water conductivity was
158 achieved. The resultant SF aqueous solution with a concentration around 0.1 g/ml was
159 used directly for the next steps. The SF aqueous solutions concentration was measured
160 by drying a controlled solution volume and weighing the residues.

161 *2.3. Porous structures processing*

162 As schematically represented in Figure 1, SF porous structures were prepared by
163 lyophilisation, but aqueous solutions were differently treated before this final step.

164

165 **Figure 1** – Schematic representation of the preparation procedures of the SF structures.

166

167 The methods involve: i) the gelation of aqueous solution, placing it statically at 25 °C for
 168 24 hours; ii) the use of the aqueous solution directly and iii) foaming aqueous solution by
 169 using a whip siphon, nitrous oxide (N_2O) as pressure gas and a nozzle of 6 cm long and
 170 1 cm diameter. Gelled and direct samples were frozen at -20 °C during 12h, while foam
 171 samples were fast freeze by liquid nitrogen. Table 1 shows the identification data of the
 172 samples, indicating also the dissolving agent, the processing method and the time elapsed
 173 since the samples are prepared until they completely freeze.

174 In order to induce the secondary structures conversion to highly stable β -crystals, all of
 175 SF structures were treated with EtOH [35]. For this, samples were immersed for 5 seconds
 176 in EtOH and dried for 12 h at room temperature. Samples treated with EtOH will be
 177 identified with the EtOH code at the end of the names presented in Table 1.

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180 **Table 1** - SF porous structures identification and main processing parameters

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Dissolving Agent</i>	<i>Processing</i>	<i>Time (h)</i>
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<i>CaCl-Gel</i>	CaCl ₂ /H ₂ O/EtOH	gelation + freezing (-20°C) lyophilisation	27-28
<i>CaCl-Lio</i>	CaCl ₂ H ₂ O/EtOH	freezing (-20°C) + lyophilisation	3-4
<i>CaCl-Foam</i>	CaCl ₂ /H ₂ O/EtOH	NO ₃ foaming + N ₂ freezing + lyophilisation	0
<i>LiBr-Gel</i>	LiBr/H ₂ O	gelation + freezing (-20°C) lyophilisation	27-28
<i>LiBr-Lio</i>	LiBr/H ₂ O	freezing (-20°C) + lyophilisation	3-4
<i>LiBr-Foam</i>	LiBr/H ₂ O	NO ₃ foaming + N ₂ freezing + lyophilisation	0
<i>CaCl-Gel- EtOH</i>	CaCl ₂ /H ₂ O/EtOH	gelation + freezing (-20°C) lyophilisation + EtOH	27-28
<i>CaCl-Lio- EtOH</i>	CaCl ₂ H ₂ O/EtOH	freezing (-20°C) + lyophilisation + EtOH	3-4
<i>CaCl-Foam- EtOH</i>	CaCl ₂ /H ₂ O/EtOH	NO ₃ foaming + N ₂ freezing + lyophilisation + EtOH	0
<i>LiBr-Gel- EtOH</i>	LiBr/H ₂ O	gelation + freezing (-20°C) lyophilisation + EtOH	27-28
<i>LiBr-Lio- EtOH</i>	LiBr/H ₂ O	freezing (-20°C) + lyophilisation + EtOH	3-4
<i>LiBr-Foam- EtOH</i>	LiBr/H ₂ O	NO ₃ foaming + N ₂ freezing + lyophilisation + EtOH	0

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183 2.4. Characterization techniques

184 The morphology of the structures was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM)
185 with a NanoSEM - FEI Nova 200 (FEG/SEM). Prior evaluation, all the samples were
186 coated by a 20 nm gold layer by magnetron sputtering with a Polaron SC502 apparatus.

187 The porosity was determined by mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP) with a
188 Quantachrome Instruments Poremaster-60 GT operating in the pressure range from 10⁻⁴
189 MPa to 414 MPa. Samples were degassed *in situ* at 110 °C for 12 h prior to the
190 measurements. A contact angle of 140° and a surface tension of 480 dyn·cm⁻¹ for mercury
191 and a pressure equilibration time of 11 s were used. The helium density measurements
192 were performed in a Quantachrome Instruments automatic Micro Ultrapycnometer.

193 Molecular insights on the different samples were studied by Attenuated Total Reflectance
194 (ATR)/Fourier Transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy with a Jasco FT/IR-4100 system
195 from 4000 to 600 cm⁻¹ using 64 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The secondary structure
196 was analyzed from ATR/FTIR data by amide I region deconvolution [36]. The data were
197 collected from the average of the measurements of three different samples. The results

198 were analyzed using one way, non-paired ANOVA (analysis of variance) with Tukey test
199 and 5 % of tolerance.

200 The crystallinity of the SF structures was obtained from X-Ray diffraction measurements
201 using a Philips X'Pert PRO diffractometer with CuK α radiation ($\lambda=1.5406\text{\AA}$) in the range
202 of $5 < 2\theta < 70^\circ$ with a step size of 0.05° and an exposure of 10 s per step.

203 Thermal stability was measured by a Thermal Gravimetric Analyzer (TGA) TGA/SDTA
204 851e Mettler Toledo apparatus at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ in the temperature range
205 from 25 to 800°C under air flow.

206 Thermal transitions were analyzed with a differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) Mettler
207 Toledo DSC 822e equipment at $10^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ from 25 to 350°C under nitrogen purge
208 ($50\text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$). In order to remove bonded water, samples were first heated at 140°C
209 during 20 min.

210 Both water uptake and water stability were measured by the same experiment. For that,
211 the weight of SF porous structures immersed in water was measured during consecutive
212 5 days. Water uptake (U %) was obtained from the relation between absorbed water and
213 initial mass, following the equation 1.

214

$$215 \quad U (\%) = \frac{M_s - M_d}{M_d} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

216 where U is the samples water uptake ability (%), M_s is the weight of the swollen sample
217 in equilibrium (g) and M_d is the weight of dried sample (g). The total water uptake was
218 obtained once samples stop absorbing water and show constant mass.

219 Water stability was measured by following the weight measurements on time, with the
220 maximum water load as reference. Samples degradation was considered when weight loss
221 is observed, while constant weight measurement signaled samples water stability.

222

223 *2.5. Adsorption test*

224 In order to carry out the pollutants adsorption experiments, 20 ppm solutions of metalloids
225 (As^{5+} , As^{3+}) and heavy metals (Cr^{6+} and Cr^{3+}) were prepared, from the following
226 precursor salts: As^{5+} - Na_2HAsO_4 ($\geq 98\%$), As^{3+} - NaAsO_2 (90 %), Cr^{6+} - $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (99.8
227 %) and Cr^{3+} - $\text{KCrSO}_4\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The solutions pH was adjusted to 4 by adding HCl and
228 NaOH diluted solution. For all the experiments the sample/solution ratio was fixed to 2
229 g/L. Thus, 10 mg of silk were added to 5 mL of solution, and mechanically stirred at room
230 temperature for 18 hours. Afterwards, silk structures were manually separated from the

231 solution, and the final concentrations of chromium and arsenic were determined by
232 slightly modified diphenylcarbazide [37, 38] and heptamolybdate [39, 40] colorimetric
233 methodologies, respectively. Absorbance of the solutions was measured by a Spectronic
234 20 Genesys UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Triplicate punctual adsorption measurements
235 were performed for all the samples.

236

237 3. Results

238 3.1. Morphological characterization

239 SEM images were used to analyse the morphology and pore microstructure of the
240 developed SF structures. Representative images of the six different samples, CaCl-Gel,
241 CaCl-Lio, CaCl-Foam, LiBr-Gel, LiBr-Lio and LiBr-Foam, are presented in Figure 2.
242 Further information related to morphology is shown as supporting information (Figure
243 S1). As can be observed, all the samples are characterized by a well-defined porous
244 structure. In addition, the shape of the pores within the different structures clearly differs
245 from one another, demonstrating the strong effect of the solvating agent and the
246 regeneration procedure on the final morphology of SF.

247

249 **Figure 2** – Representative SEM images of the SF porous structures: a) CaCl₂-Gel b)
250 CaCl₂-Lio c) CaCl₂-Foam d) LiBr-Gel e) LiBr-Lio and f) LiBr-Foam. g) LiBr-Lio sample
251 after EtOH treatment. The scale is valid for all images. The colours were added digitally.

252 Figure 2a shows the morphology of CaCl₂-Gel sample, which is dominated by a highly
253 branched network of fibrils. Each SF-based fibril is formed by elongated structures of 1-
254 2 μm in thickness connected to globular structures of 2-3 μm of diameter. The set forms
255 a bean-like structure with interconnected and continuous pores ranging from 20 μm to 40
256 μm of diameter.

257 Both Gel samples were equally processed but with varying the solvent. This change leads
258 to the formation of a completely different microstructure (Figure 2d). LiBr-Gel samples
259 are composed by two-dimensional non-compact sheets, packed in a leaf-like
260 macrostructure (Figure S1d) with an interconnected continuous pore system. The planar
261 sheets of LiBr-Gel are characterized by a thickness between 200 - 400 nm with
262 interspersed pores in the 2 μm to 20 μm diameter range, leading to a pore system with
263 two pores levels.

264 Figures 2b and 2e show the morphology of CaCl₂-Lio and LiBr-Lio samples, respectively,
265 both characterized by a leaf-like macrostructure (Figures S1b and S1e, respectively), but
266 different microstructure. The morphology of the CaCl₂-Lio sample is formed by wide
267 two-dimensional planar structures of 7-8 μm thickness, interspersed by small and
268 homogeneously distributed pores of 1-2 μm diameter (Figure 2b). LiBr-Lio sample on the
269 contrary, is composed by narrow planar structures with a thickness of 1-3 μm that fold in
270 specific locations to form a sponge like/ honeycomb regions with irregular pores of 4-15
271 μm diameter (Figure 2e). In both cases, the existence of two-porosity levels leads to an
272 overall porous structure with highly interconnected cavities.

273 Regarding the structures obtained by the N₂O foaming method, the morphology of the
274 CaCl₂-Foam and LiBr-Foam samples (Figures 2c and 2f, respectively) also shows a leaf-
275 like shape macrostructure. The main difference between the two samples is found in the
276 thickness of the flat sheets, varying between 2 μm and 7 μm for the CaCl₂-Foam samples
277 and between 300-600 nm for the LiBr-Foam samples. Contrary to Gel and Lio samples,
278 Foam samples do not show interspersed pores.

279 The effect of EtOH treatment on the porous SF structures can be observed in Figure 2g
280 for the LiBr-Lio structure, being representative for the rest of the structures. After the
281 treatment with EtOH, samples retain the porous structure, but with slight variations in the
282 planar sheets conformation and a certain increase of the pore size.

283 Further insights on the structural characteristics of the samples were studied after mercury
 284 intrusion porosimetry, allowing to obtaining density, surface area and total porosity, as
 285 presented in Table 2.

286 **Table 2** - Degree of porosity, density and surface area of the different SF-based
 287 structures (“-“ indicates the lack of measurable data).

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Micropore size (μm)</i>	<i>Total porosity (%)</i>	<i>He density (g/cm^3)</i>	<i>Surface area (m^2/g)</i>	<i>Specific surface area ($10^7 \text{m}^2/\text{m}^3$)</i>
<i>CaCl₂-Gel</i>	20-40	94.0	1.34	71.1	4.47
<i>CaCl₂-Lio</i>	1-2	97.8	1.31	108.8	8.31
<i>CaCl₂-Foam</i>	-	94.9	1.42	45.5	3.20
<i>LiBr-Gel</i>	2-20	94.3	1.46	86.1	5.90
<i>LiBr-Lio</i>	4-15	93.7	1.64	59.6	3.63
<i>LiBr-Foam</i>	-	95.9	1.44	122.8	8.53

288

289 Regardless preparation procedure, the degree of porosity varies between 94% and 98%,
 290 which is significantly higher than the reported porosity values of comparable porous
 291 structures based on SF, which generally range between 70% and 90% [11, 16].

292 The specific surface areas range from $3.2 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ to $8.53 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$, which are also
 293 higher than the values obtained for SF non-woven mats, commonly used for the
 294 preparation of membranes for environmental remediation [16, 17].

295 Mercury (Hg) intrusion curves as a function of pore diameter for the different structures
 296 were collected in Supporting Figure 2, showing that the intrusion values range between 1
 297 and 300 μm , that indicates that all SF samples can be classified as macro-porous.

298 The main contributions to the final porosity differ between the different samples
 299 (Supporting Figure 2). *CaCl₂-Gel* and *LiBr-Gel* samples show a pore distribution mainly
 300 centered at 13 μm pore diameter. But, *CaCl₂-Gel* shows intrusion signals at 30 μm , while
 301 *LiBr-Gel* shows them in the region above 1 μm . These data suggest that even when the
 302 two gel samples are highly dominated by 13 μm diameter pores, there are also relevant
 303 contributions of larger pores in the case of *CaCl₂-Gel* and smaller pores in *LiBr-Gel*, in
 304 good agreement with the microstructure observed at the corresponding SEM images
 305 (Figure 2).

306 *CaCl₂-Lio* and *LiBr-Lio* samples show peaks with a maximum at 54 μm , being also
 307 contributions of even larger pores (around 200 μm) in both cases. Thus, the Lio process
 308 leads to average larger pore sizes. The slight signal in the region of smaller pore diameters

309 on CaCl₂-Lio sample can be related to the secondary pores observed in the SEM images
310 (Figure 2b).

311 Finally, the intrusion results from CaCl₂-Foam and LiBr-Foam samples show a width and
312 oscillatory signal ranging between 0.8 to 200 μm. This signals that, in contrast to Gel and
313 Lio samples, with pores size defined at 13 and 200 μm respectively, the pores of Foam
314 samples are not in a controlled diameter range.

315

316 *3.2. Molecular and structural variations*

317 FTIR measurements were performed to evaluate the molecular conformations of SF in
318 the different samples (Figure 3). As can be observed in Figure 3a, regardless of the solvent
319 agent and processing method, the main absorption bands characteristic of SF, amide I -
320 1620 cm⁻¹, amide II - 1517 cm⁻¹ and amide III - 1235 cm⁻¹ remain unaltered. Comparing
321 the FTIR spectra, the unique difference relies on the appearance of new absorption bands
322 located at 2850 cm⁻¹ (marked by black arrow), found for CaCl₂-Gel and LiBr-Gel
323 samples.

324 Figure 3b shows the deconvolution of the FTIR spectra in the amide I region, providing
325 information on the secondary organization [36]. The possible secondary conformations
326 are α-helix (A), β-sheets (B) and β-turns (T) belonging to crystalline domains and random
327 coils (RC) and non-bonded side chains (SC) belonging to amorphous region. Each one,
328 can be classified inside Amide I region according to its maximum wavenumber, in the
329 following way: T (1696-1663 cm⁻¹), A (1662-1656 cm⁻¹), RC (1655-1638 cm⁻¹), B (1637-
330 1616 cm⁻¹ and 1705-1695 cm⁻¹) and SC (1615-1605 cm⁻¹) [41]. The presence of each
331 conformation was calculated by adding the area under the curve of all the peaks
332 corresponding to the same conformation.

333 Figure 3b shows two examples of the FTIR amide I deconvolution. In the upper part, a
334 typical example of amorphous SF is presented where the maximum is located in the RC
335 region. The lower part of Figure 3 shows an example of a highly crystalline SF structure,
336 with maximum value in the B region, corresponding to β-sheet conformation.

337

338

339 **Figure 3** – For the different SF structures: a) FTIR absorbance curves, b) amide I
 340 deconvolution of the amorphous structure (above) and crystalline structure (below), c)
 341 band assignment and d) band assignment of SF-EtOH treated samples.

342 Figures 3c shows the secondary conformation of SF structures. Differences are observed
 343 among them, showing the influence of the processing conditions on the SF secondary
 344 structure and therefore, on the final properties of materials. In order to analyze those
 345 differences, statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) under 5% of tolerance has been
 346 applied. Due to their influence on SF properties, β -sheets (B) content and the relation
 347 between B and random coil (RC) structures have been considered as the most important
 348 parameters to analyze by this method. Regarding to the ability of the different processing
 349 methods to promote β -sheets into SF structure, it is only observed a significant difference
 350 ($p < 0.05$) in Gelled samples, where followed processing seems to have major ability to

351 induce B structures (between 32 and 34%). Regarding to the relation between B and RC,
352 it is observed a significant difference in lyophilized samples, which are clearly dominated
353 by RC (~45%). In any case, no significant difference ($p>0.05$) between solving agents
354 was observed.

355 The effect of EtOH treatment over SF porous structures is presented in Figure 3d.
356 Following with ANOVA statistical analysis, it can be observed that there exist a
357 significant increase of B structures (reaching to values around 40-45%), when SF
358 samples are treated with EtOH. The achieved similar values for β -structures in all the
359 samples, suggest the homogenous effect of EtOH over SF.

360 To analyze crystalline structures condition, X-ray data was used. It is important to
361 consider that SF is formed by macromolecular chains, and therefore, it is unable to adopt
362 a perfect crystalline structure with well-defined order. In contrast, SF crystallization is
363 associated with the partial alignment of the molecular chains. This pseudo-packing leads
364 to wide diffraction patterns, accompanied by superimposed broad peaks ascribed to the not
365 ordered regions. Further, the plasticization level of crystalline structures, represents a
366 certain variability of crystalline spacing and consequently it is common to observe a slight
367 displacement of diffraction peaks among samples [42, 43]. Figure 4 shows the X-ray
368 diffraction patterns of the different samples. SF porous structures seem to reveal five
369 different diffraction peaks at 12.4° , 14.5° , 20.1° , 24.9° and 28.5° , which do not necessarily
370 appear in all samples. Peaks 12° - 13° , 14° - 15° and $>28^\circ$ are commonly related with silk I
371 structures [44], while the presence of peaks at 20 - 21° and 24 - 25° is ascribed to highly
372 packed silk II conformations [44, 45]. The apparent lack of silk III representative peaks
373 suggests that the used processing methods do not promote these structures, mainly
374 ascribed to water-air interfaces.

375

376

377 **Figure 4** - X-ray diffraction patterns of a) SF porous samples and b) EtOH treated SF
378 porous samples.

379

380 X-ray data suggest that i) processing methodology induces different ordering on
381 crystalline structures, ii) Lio samples show the higher disorder degree, as revealed the
382 broader diffraction peaks and iii) LiBr samples show more non-stabilized Silk I
383 structures, as revealed by the well-defined diffraction maxima observed around 12.4, 14.5
384 and 28.5° in 2θ (Figure 4a).

385 From the crystallographic structural point of view, the EtOH post-treatment of the
386 samples has two side effects. Firstly, it modifies the crystals patterns of all the samples
387 situating theirs maximum at 20-21° in 2θ , ascribed to Silk II structure. Secondly the broad
388 diffraction signals ascribed to amorphous disorder domains is reduced.

389

390 *3.3. Thermal behaviour*

391 The thermal behavior of the SF structures was studied by TGA and DSC (Figure 5). The
392 TGA results (Figures 5a and 5b) show a similar weight loss profile as a function of
393 temperature for all samples. Before 100 °C, porous SF undergo a first weight loss due to
394 water evaporation. Then, the weight of the samples remains constant until 290 °C,
395 temperature at which SF starts to degrade due to the side chains breakdown and peptide
396 bonds cleavage [46, 47]. Finally, around 330 °C the combustion of the organic compounds
397 starts, and it is completed at around 600 °C. The main difference between samples is
398 found during water evaporation step (<100 °C), in where CaCl₂ processed samples show
399 a weight loss around 10% and LiBr samples around 5% .

400 The treatment with EtOH, on the contrary, promotes larger variations in the thermal
401 degradation profiles (Figure 5a and 5b). On one side, EtOH treated samples show a minor
402 weight decrease during the water loss step. On the other side, it can be observed that the
403 following degradation steps shift to higher temperatures (from 290 °C to 300 °C),
404 including complete combustion process, which ends at 615 °C [48].

405

406 **Figure 5** - TGA and DSC thermograms for CaCl₂-Gel, CaCl₂-Lio and CaCl₂-Foam
 407 samples (a and c) and LiBr-Gel, LiBr-Lio and LiBr-Foam samples (b and d), both pristine
 408 and treated with EtOH.

409 The thermal transitions of SF could be hidden by the endothermic peak related to the
 410 water evaporation. Thus, previous to the DSC measurements, water was removed from
 411 the samples by 20 min isothermal heating at 140 °C. The DSC scans performed after that
 412 procedure are shown in Figure 5c and 5d. The main characteristic transitions of SF are a
 413 glass transition temperature (T_g) around 185 °C, ascribed to amorphous domains motion
 414 [47], a recrystallization temperature (T_c) found as a exothermic peak between 210 - 235
 415 °C, attributed to the amorphous domains folding into β-sheet crystalline regions and the
 416 degradation peak above 250 °C, related to the beginning of the side chains and peptide
 417 bonds thermal decomposition. The slight endothermic peak that can be observed in some
 418 samples before glass transition is related to the evaporation of remaining bounded water
 419 molecules [47].

420 As observed, Lio samples showed a well defined T_g and T_c, while the same transitions
 421 are slightly or non-visible in the other samples (Figure 5a and 5b).

422 After EtOH treatment, the thermal behavior becomes homogenous for all samples (dashed
 423 line in Figures 5c and 5d) and all thermal transitions of the porous structures disappeared
 424 which is directly related to the crystallization of amorphous domains (Figure 3).

425

426 3.4. Water uptake and stability

427 In order to apply SF-based porous materials for water pollution remediation purposes, it
 428 is highly desirable to fully understand samples behaviour in wet environments.
 429 Henceforth, water uptake and the water stability were measured.

430

431 **Figure 6-** SF porous samples: a) water uptake, b) Cr³⁺ adsorption.

432

433 Water uptake was monitored during the first 180 min of immersion (Figure 6a). Samples
 434 water saturation point is shown in Supporting Figure 3a. As can be observed all the porous
 435 structures, reach a water uptake saturation after 20 minutes of immersion. Data point out
 436 the major adsorption of CaCl-Gel samples, with 24g/ml adsorption.

437 EtOH treated samples water uptake data is collected in Supporting Figures 3a and 3b. As
 438 can be observed, after EtOH treatment, water uptake appears to be reduced in all the cases,
 439 while water absorption speed and retention ability remains constant.

440 Water stability of SF structures was analysed by measuring the weight of the porous
 441 membranes after reached the maximum water uptake (Supporting Figure 3c). Data were
 442 collected for 3 consecutive weeks. After water immersion, practically all the samples
 443 show no significant weight loss, showing an excellent good stability. The CaCl₂-Lio
 444 sample was the only exception, resulting in a partial weight loss of nearly 50% of the total
 445 mass.

446 After treatment with EtOH, the porous structures conserve their water stability, even for
447 the CaCl₂-Lio sample which becomes water stable. Results confirming the EtOH ability
448 to stabilize SF structures (Supporting Figure 3d).

449

450 *3.5. Heavy metals adsorption*

451 The ability of the different porous SF structures to remove heavy metals from water was
452 measured by water adsorption. SF samples were initially analysed versus different
453 metalloids and heavy metal species: As³⁺, As⁵⁺, Cr⁶⁺ and Cr³⁺. Supporting Figure 4,
454 collects the LiBr-Foam sample adsorption capacities as representative for all the samples.
455 The initial results indicate that significant pollutant reduction is attained just in the case
456 of Cr³⁺. To understand the effect of the morphology and the physical-chemical properties
457 of porous SF structures in the Cr³⁺ adsorption ability, the adsorption capacity of each
458 sample before and after EtOH treatment was analysed. The obtained adsorption results
459 are represented in Figure 6b.

460 Figure 6b shows that all samples allow significant adsorption of Cr³⁺, between 0.7 and
461 1.65 mg of Cr³⁺ per g of SF, indicating the suitable characteristics of the developed SF
462 structures for water applications [49]. The maximum retention values, slightly below 20%
463 of the total concentration, were observed for the samples processed as foams (CaCl₂-Foam
464 and LiBr-Foam).

465 Further, the Cr³⁺ adsorption nearly doubles for all samples after the EtOH treatment, (1.2
466 and 3.1 mg/g). Once again, the maximum adsorption values are observed in the Foam
467 samples, with adsorption values above 30% of the initial concentration.

468

469 **4. Discussion**

470 Silk fibroin porous structures have been processed following diverse procedures,
471 including different solving agents, processing and post-processing. In the following, i)
472 the origin of each morphology, ii) the effects of the processing and obtained
473 microstructure on the physical-chemical properties of the material and iii) the potentials
474 of the SF porous structures on water remediation will be discussed.

475

476 *4.1. SF porous structures formation*

477 During the solvating, Ca^{2+} and Li^+ cations from CaCl_2 and LiBr respectively, form chelates
478 with SF carbonyl and hydroxyl groups, disrupting the intra- and intermolecular forces
479 that keep the SF structure packed (Figure 7a1) [50]. Taking advance from the disruption,
480 water molecules flow inside SF structure and form new H-bonds, leading to completely
481 amorphous and opened SF conformation (Figure 7a2). In this point, SF molecules are free
482 to interact with water generated polar environment [51] (Figure 7b1) and due to the SF
483 amphiphilic behavior, the polypeptide chains adopt micelles-like structures, in where
484 hydrophilic domains occupy the shell and hydrophobic blocks the core (Figure 7b2) [52].
485 As H. Cho *et al.* [53] described, during SF solution, strong ionic force of CaCl_2 , promotes
486 the polypeptide chains scission into smaller chains. As a consequence, when SF micelles
487 are formed, the small polypeptide sections aggregate, leading to molecules with high
488 hydrodynamic radius (ranging from 100 to 300 nm). On the contrary, this effect is not
489 observable for LiBr solutions, in where SF molecules self-assemble to form micelles with
490 smaller hydrodynamic radius (10 to 30nm) (Figure 7b2) [53]. During micelles folding,
491 water molecules could get trapped inside, hindering the hydrophobic interactions and
492 delaying structures complete packing.

493 When SF solution is freeze, due to SF/water solution eutectic point, the formed pure water
494 ice crystals exclude the SF micelles, grouping them into ice crystal walls (Figure 7b3).
495 The increasing SF concentration, favors the protein-protein interactions, giving place to
496 a continuous phase formation, as observed in sheet-like structures of SEM images (Figure
497 2) [54]. The definitive porous structure is formed once ice crystals are removed by
498 lyophilization, leaving the planar structures without further changes [54] (Figure 7b4).

499 As a result of the CaCl_2 micelles larger size, when they are accumulated into the ice
500 crystals walls, thicker structures than those formed from LiBr smaller micelles are
501 promoted (Figure 7b4). This effect, explains the difference on sheet-like structures
502 thickness observed between samples processed by CaCl_2 and LiBr solutions (Figure 2).

503 The nature of secondary order micro-pores, is related to the growth of secondary ice
504 crystals embedded in highly concentrated SF regions [54]. Their size and shape respond
505 to the dimensions of planar structures in where they are formed. The thicker structures
506 formed in CaCl_2 samples represent a higher resistance to ice crystals growth than the
507 narrower structures formed by LiBr processing. Thus, the formed secondary crystals from
508 CaCl_2 ternary solution, adopt smaller and more regular shapes while secondary ice
509 crystals of LiBr processed samples, with less resistance, facilitate the formation of bigger
510 and more irregular pores. The lack of secondary pores on Foam planar structures, reveals

511 that the faster freezing process of liquid nitrogen bath, does not provide enough time to
512 form secondary ice crystals. The irregularity of foam samples pores sizes, could be related
513 to N₂O gas molecules induced non-controlled cavities (Supporting Figure 2) [31].

514 The bean-like structure observed in CaCl-Gel samples is the one exception with respect
515 to the microstructure (SEM images Figure 2 and SFigure 1). Taking into consideration
516 the given additional time for gelation (table 1), the observed bean-like structures must be
517 related with molecular reorganization processes (Figure 7c). SF micelles have a tendency
518 to group based on the formation of inter- and intramolecular interactions along the protein
519 chains, including hydrophobic interactions and hydrogen bonds [29] (Figure 7c3). As
520 described Z. Chen *et al.* [55] eventually, when SF micelles have enough time to interact
521 one each other, they start growing in the form of elongated structures of repetitive
522 micelles (Figure 7c4). These structures are named nano-fibrils and due to additional
523 micelles junctions, nano-fibrils continue growing and branching until the formation of
524 interconnected network (Figure 7c5) [55]. While fibrils remain still in solution, the water
525 molecules trapped inside the micelles hinder the formation of crystalline structures [56].
526 However, when sufficient time for molecular interactions is given (as happened in Gel
527 samples), the hydrophobic interactions finally happen, promoting the ordered domains
528 packing into B ordered domains, which stabilize the structure and avoid its
529 resolubilization [57] (Figure 7c6). During freeze, the formed fibrils will be slightly
530 compacted by ice crystals grow (Figure 7c7), but due to the achieved stability, the
531 network still remains unalterable (Figure 7c8). The larger micelles from CaCl₂ ternary
532 solution seem to be the responsible of inducing more contacts between micelles, favoring
533 larger hydrophobic interactions between them and supporting the fibrils network
534 formation process in CaCl₂-Gel samples [57].

535

536

537

538 **Figure 7** - Graphical representation of Silk Fibroin (SF) a) aqueous solution (β -sheets
 539 disruption), b) CaCl₂ and LiBr salts effect during solution and c) gelation process.

540

541 4.2. Processing effect on SF properties.

542 As it is shown in FTIR and XRD data, the secondary structure and crystallinity highly
 543 differ between samples. In Gel samples, the given longer molecular recombination time,
 544 promotes the formation of crystalline structures rich in β -sheets. These results also agree
 545 with the observed low intensity FTIR peaks at 2850 cm⁻¹ in Gel samples (CaCl-Gel and
 546 LiBr-Gel), attributed to hydrogen bonding increase due to chains packing [29]. The

547 shorter time for molecular recombination of Lio samples, results in slightly ordered
548 structures with high RC amount (amorphous conformation). These data confirm the
549 strong effect of molecular recombination time for SF structure formation.

550 Foam samples present differentiated secondary structure and crystallinity (Figures 3 and
551 4), even though both samples have equally processed. As described by *D. Maniglio et al.*
552 [31] the SF foam is formed at the time that aqueous solution is extruded through the
553 nozzle. Also, foam was immediately freeze by liquid nitrogen bath. This leaves the SF
554 molecules without time for molecular recombination (Table 1). Thus, it can be suggested
555 that during foaming process, the higher micelles from CaCl₂ ternary solution, promote
556 more protein-protein interactions than LiBr solution. Consequently, in CaCl₂-Foam the
557 hydrophobic interactions are promoted and more crystalline domains are formed.

558 Processing methods induced molecular organization, as is described by TGA data, seems
559 to slightly affect samples thermal stability. However, a difference is observed between
560 solvents induced water retention, having the samples from CaCl₂ ternary solution greater
561 water amount (Figure 5a and 5b). Data suggest that bigger micelles formed in CaCl₂
562 ternary solution, retain a higher amount of water molecules inside, plasticising the
563 resulting samples.

564 DSC data shows a clear effect of processing on thermal transitions. As can be observed,
565 amorphous samples show the more pronounced transitions (both T_g and T_c), while
566 crystalline samples, practically lack them. Both T_g and T_c, are transitions related to free
567 domains mobility. Chains packing and consequent B structures presence, suppose the
568 formation of a cross-linked network in where the chains mobility is reduced by physical
569 nodes. As a consequence, greater B structures presence implies a minor mobility and
570 therefore, less pronounced thermal transitions.

571 No experimental evidence was found to relate the water uptake with the secondary
572 structure of SF. This suggests that the influence of microstructure prevails over the
573 secondary structure for water absorbance and retention, being the bean-like structure of
574 CaCl₂-Gel sample the configuration with major water retention ability.

575 The good stability of SF porous samples in water, confirm the potentiality of samples for
576 wet applications. CaCl₂-Lio sample is the only one not water stable, even when it has a
577 similar secondary conformation and crystalline organization than LiBr-Lio samples. The
578 main parameter which differs among both Lio samples is found on micelles formation
579 and the plasticisation level of the samples, being the CaCl₂-Lio the most plasticised one.

580 Data reveal once again the importance of the solvent contribution over samples properties
581 and predict a water stability decrease with an increase on plasticisation.

582 Regarding to the effect of EtOH treatment, it is revealed a homogenous influence over
583 almost all the parameters. It is known that EtOH highly interacts with water molecules,
584 even more than SF (Figure 8a1). As consequence, during EtOH bath the H₂O molecules
585 could link to EtOH. During drying process, due to this interactions bonded water and
586 EtOH molecules are evaporated together, leaving the SF free of water. This SF
587 dehydration, derives in more hydrophobic interactions, chains packing and crystalline
588 domains increase (Figure 8a2) [35]. This effect, could be noted i) in SEM images where
589 due to EtOH treatment, porous structures are contracted; ii) in FTIR and XRD, where the
590 treated samples become highly crystalline Silk II (Figure 3 and 4); iii) in TGA where,
591 thermal degradation was slightly delayed (Figure 5); iv) in DSC where highly stable and
592 low mobile crystal domains lead to thermal transitions almost total loss (Figure 5) and v)
593 in water behavior where all the structures gain water stability (Figure 6) .

594 The only characteristic not homogeneously influenced by EtOH treatment was the water
595 uptake ability. This heterogeneity can be ascribed to the higher influence of the
596 microstructure on water absorption. The observed water uptake decreasing with respect
597 to EtOH untreated samples, (Supporting Figure 3a), is related to the structure contraction
598 due to the dehydration (Figure 2g).

599

600 *4.3. SF porous structures potentiality for water remediation.*

601 Finally, SF adsorption ability for different heavy metal and metalloid ions, including As⁵⁺,
602 As³⁺, Cr⁶⁺ and Cr³⁺ was studied. The selection of these ions is based on their varied
603 chemistry and high toxicity in aqueous environments. In waters with pH 4, As⁵⁺ and Cr⁶⁺
604 are usually stabilized as negatively charged oxyanions like arsenate, chromate or
605 dichromate [58]. On the contrary, Cr³⁺ is a hard cation that is stabilized as aquo-oxo
606 species (Cr(OH)²⁺ and Cr³⁺) with neat positive charges [59]. Finally, As³⁺ is stabilized as
607 neutral species. In general the ions adsorption is driven by: i) electrostatic interaction with
608 charged groups within the porous structure; ii) by anionic or cationic exchange processes
609 where mobile ions within the SF structure could be replaced and iii) or direct interaction
610 with reactive species. As adsorption data reveal (Figure S4), SF is affine to cationic
611 species (Cr(OH)²⁺ and Cr³⁺), while practically does not show affinity for negative or
612 neutral species. This behaviour, suggests an electrostatic interaction between SF and
613 cationic species (Cr(OH)²⁺ and Cr³⁺), mainly ascribed to the negative charge of SF

614 surface, result of isoelectric point differences between hydrophilic and terminal domains
 615 [16, 60, 61] (Figure 8a1). Additionally, it can be predicted that SF and $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ will form
 616 direct interactions between reactive $-\text{OH}$ group of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and accessible amine groups
 617 of SF polypeptide chain, increasing the porous structures adsorption capacity (**Kinetics
 618 and equilibrium study for the adsorption of textile dyes on coconut shell activated
 619 carbon**)(**Chromium speciation in Zr-based Metal-Organic Frameworks for
 620 environmental remediation**).

621

622 **Figure 8.** a) EtOH bath effect b) metals adsorption improvement by N_2O addition.

623

624 With respect to the effects of SF secondary structure and morphological characteristics in
 625 heavy metals adsorption, it can be stated that: i) Foam samples show larger adsorption
 626 values and ii) SF porous structures adsorption practically doubles after EtOH treatment.
 627 The higher adsorption ability of the Foam samples must be related to the processing
 628 conditions. During the foaming, SF is mixed with N_2O in order to generate pores by
 629 decompression. The gas molecules get trapped within the SF polypeptide chains forming
 630 interactions with chelate and hydroxyl groups [62] (Figure 8b2) [63]. Thus, it can be
 631 hypothesized that, these new SF- N_2O complexes may generate more accessible points in
 632 where $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ could link, increasing the SF adsorption capacity (Figure 8b2).
 633 Regarding to Cr^{3+} adsorption after EtOH treatment, it seems that all the samples undergo
 634 an increase of their capacity. To explain this change, three considerations have been

635 taking into consideration after EtOH treatment: i) all the samples do not reach a
636 homogenous behavior, suggesting the effect of microstructure as additional factor; ii) the
637 Cr^{3+} adsorption capacity increases despite of the decrease of samples water uptake (note
638 that CaCl₂-Gel sample in spite of having the major water uptake does not have the major
639 Cr^{3+} adsorption capacity) and; iii) SF negative charges did not increase during chains
640 packing, discarding the electrostatic interactions as the single reason for this effect [64].
641 Thus, we hypothesize that the dehydration caused by EtOH bath, generates new
642 accessible polar bonding points (where H₂O molecules were attached) in where more
643 $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ could be attached.
644 In this context, it can be concluded that, in SF porous structures, Cr^{3+} adsorption is mainly
645 driven by direct interactions. However, while H₂O molecules remain bonded to the
646 polypeptide structure (before EtOH treatment), the adsorption is driven by the
647 combination of electrostatic and direct interactions.
648 The obtained adsorption results, can be compared with the ones from different natural
649 materials presented in Table 3. Actually few works focused on As and Cr absorption can
650 be found, of which still less, work with silk as adsorbent. As can be observed, most of the
651 efforts have focused on use accessible, cheap and controlled materials, i.e chitosan,
652 cellulose, plants or minerals. The present work demonstrates that SF is a promising
653 material, competitive with the aforementioned ones, to be used as adsorption material for
654 different pollutants remove. In addition, the given routes for SF based porous structures
655 control, in with the proven SF capacity for composite materials developments (auto ref?),
656 lead to a huge road for this new materials improving.

657

658 **Table 3.** Representative data of different natural materials used for heavy metals
659 adsorption.

<i>Adsorbent</i>	<i>Morphology</i>	<i>Pollutant / concentration (mg/L)</i>	<i>Charge (g/L)</i>	<i>Adsorption (mg/g)</i>	<i>ref</i>
<i>modified chitosan</i>	crosslinked	Methylated Ar / 125	0.5	7.1 – 15.5	1
<i>Cocoa shells</i>	fibers	Cu / 45.5	40	2.6	2
<i>Aluminosilicate geopolymer</i>	powder	Pb, Ni, Hg Cu / 3000	5	200 - 600	3
<i>wood</i>	sawdust	Zn, Fe, Cu / 10	10	0.6 - 1	4
<i>wool keratose /silk fibroin</i>	Electrospinning mats	Cu^{2+} / 3.49	-	2.88	5
<i>SF</i>	Electrospinning mats	Cu^{2+} / 3.49	-	1.65	5

<i>Malic acid/ chitosan</i>	hydrogel beads	Cr(VI) / 100	1	383.2	6
<i>waste cotton</i>	cross-linked hydrogel	Pb / 7.6	1	7.5	7
<i>This work</i>	Porous	Cr ³⁺ / 20	2	3.1	-

660

- 661 1- Uptake of methylated arsenic by a polymeric adsorbent: Process performance and
662 adsorption chemistry
- 663 2- Selection of a natural sorbent to remove toxic metals from acidic leachate produced
664 during soil decontamination
- 665 3- A green, porous and eco-friendly magnetic geopolymer adsorbent for heavy metals
666 removal from aqueous solutions
- 667 4- A study of sorption heavy metals by natural organic sorbents
- 668 5- Nanofibrous membrane of wool keratose/silk fibroin blend for heavy metal ion
669 adsorption
- 670 6- Malic acid-enhanced chitosan hydrogel beads (mCHBs) for the removal of Cr(VI) and
671 Cu(II) from aqueous solution
- 672 7- Fast adsorption of heavy metal ions by waste cotton fabrics based double network
673 hydrogel and influencing factors insight

674

675

676 5. Conclusions

677 In order to expand the natural based materials applicability, the effect of different
678 processing methods on Silk Fibroin (SF) porous structures properties has been addressed.
679 For this purpose, six different SF structures with highly differentiated microstructure and
680 porosity values above 94% were obtained from two dissolving agents, CaCl₂ and LiBr
681 and three different regeneration procedures, including gelation, freezing and N₂O
682 foaming.

683 It has been observed that CaCl₂/EtOH/H₂O ternary solution promotes SF molecules
684 aggregation, increases the samples plasticization and induces the formation of wider leaf-
685 like structures. On the contrary, LiBr aqueous solution favors the formation of thinner
686 leaf-like structures with bigger interspersed pores.

687 SF gelation promotes molecular recombination, enables the polypeptide chains folding
688 into highly crystallized structures and in combination with CaCl₂/EtOH/H₂O ternary
689 solution, results in a bean-like microstructure. Directly lyophilized samples, contrary,
690 promote amorphous structures and combined with LiBr solution, enable the formation of
691 water soluble structures.

692 SF shows affinity for cationic species, which could be favored by N₂O gas foaming. EtOH
693 treatment, leads to an increase of SF crystalline configuration that slightly slows down

694 thermal degradation, increases samples water stability and promotes the ability for Cr³⁺
695 adsorption.

696 This demonstrated SF ability for heavy metals removal, as well as the capacity for
697 controlling SF properties through processing, open a novel and promising investigation
698 approach for the applicability of natural based materials and high SF porous materials
699 aptitude for water remediation purposes.

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